

Extraction Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with β -Mercaptopropanoic Acid Anilide and its Applications

CHANDRIMA RAY and JYOTIRMOY DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

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Small quantities (11-68 μg) of cobalt have been extracted into chloroform as the 1 : 3 complex with β -mercaptopropanoic acid anilide from solutions of pH 5.3-10.5 containing γ -picoline. The molar absorptivity of the red complex, measured at 480 nm is $1.33 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Cobalt has been determined in the extract with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 1.6\%$. The complex is stable up to two months, and sufficient amounts of Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , V^{5+} , Ce^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , W^{6+} , Na, K, chloride or nitrate are tolerated. However, the separation from Be^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , As^{3+} , Th^{4+} , or U^{6+} has been effected using suitable masking agents. For the determination of the composition of the complex, solid complex has been isolated and elemental analysis, magnetic measurements and IR spectral studies have been performed. The method has been used to determine cobalt in ores, alloys and medicinal samples.

THIOGLYCOLIC acid^{1,2} and its anilides^{3,4} have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt. But the stability as well as the range of the metal determined in case thioglycolic acid is low. In the present work, β -mercaptopropanoic acid anilide has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt. This method permits the determination of cobalt in the presence of ten-fold excess of nickel

Experimental

β -Mercaptopropanoic acid anilide: The reagent was prepared by refluxing a mixture of β -mercaptopropanoic acid (A.R., Fluka) and freshly distilled aniline in 1 : 1 proportion on a hot oil-bath (115-125°) for 3.5 h under an air condenser. The reagent was solidified by evaporation. When recrystallised from aqueous ethanol the compound was obtained as white crystalline needles, m.p. 80° (Found: N, 7.7; C, 59.38; H, 6.1; S, 17.75. Calcd. for: N, 7.73; C, 59.66; H, 6.07; S, 16.67%); ν_{max} 3300 (NH) and 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Standard cobalt(II) solution: Cobalt sulphate (AnalaR) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid. The cobalt content of the solution was determined gravimetrically with α -nitroso- β -naphthol⁵. Finally, the solution was suitably diluted ($\sim 10^{-4} M$).

All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

γ -Picoline: A 10% stock solution of γ -picoline (AnalaR) was prepared by dissolving γ -picoline in aqueous ethanol.

Procedure for cobalt(II): A known amount of a standard solution containing 11-68 μg of cobalt was

taken and the reagent solution (2 ml) followed by 10% γ -picoline (2 ml) were added. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.2 by the addition of aqueous ammonia. The cobalt complex was extracted with chloroform (2 $\times$ 5 ml). The two organic layers were taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask, the volume adjusted to mark with a few drops of chloroform and dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the red extract was measured at 480 nm using solvent blank.

Procedure for the determination of cobalt in ore, alloy and vitamin samples: The ore (limonite) and the alloy were decomposed by following standard methods⁶. The ore (0.9-1.2 g) was decomposed by nitric acid and potassium chlorate. The solution was taken in 100 ml measuring flask and ammonium fluoride (0.2 g) was added. Finally, the volume was made up to mark with dilute hydrochloric acid and an aliquot of 5 ml of the solution was used for the determination of cobalt. The alloy (0.9-1.0 g) was decomposed by nitric acid and hydrochloric acid (1 : 3) mixture. Tartaric acid (~ 0.15 g) was added to the resulting solution and the volume was made to 100 ml in a measuring flask. 1 ml portion of a ten-fold diluted solution was used for the determination of cobalt. Two ampules (2 $\times$ 2 ml) of Macraberin Forte injection (Glaxo Lab., Bombay) were decomposed in a covered beaker with nitric acid following a standard procedure⁶ for such samples by heating first at low temperature to avoid violent reaction. The mixture was cooled when reaction subsided and heated again with further nitric acid. The temperature was gradually raised

and finally the residue was heated to about 400° on a hot-plate. The ash was dissolved in dilute nitric acid (1:1) and evaporated slowly (1-2 h) on a steam-bath. Finally, the residue was taken in 25 ml water to which nitric acid was added in 0.25 ml portions until a clear solution was obtained on gentle heating. The cobalt content of this solution was determined by the procedure described above.

The results of analysis of samples of limonite (containing 0.5-0.6% Co) were within 1.5-2.0%. While in case of alloys (Co, 5.3%) the error was 0.4%. The results were within 1.4% in case of the medicinal sample.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance values of several extracts containing varying amount of cobalt were recorded on a Beckmann DB 4500 spectrophotometer against solvent blank as the reagent has no absorbance above 290 nm. The curves indicate that λ_{max} of cobalt complex was at 480 nm. The λ_{max} for the reagent was at 245 nm.

Chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent as 96% of the complex was extracted in the first step. The extent of extraction of the complex in isoamyl alcohol or isobutyl methyl ketone was very low and almost nil in benzene and carbon disulphide. The colour of the chloroform extract was found to be stable for more than 2 months. The experimental results showed that the extraction was complete in the range pH 5.3-10.5. Above pH 10.5 an emulsion was formed during extraction. It was observed that 5 mg reagent was sufficient for the quantitative complexation in aqueous layers. However, a ten-fold excess of the reagent had no adverse effect on the determination of cobalt. It was observed that complete extraction was possible in the presence of γ -picoline.

Optimum concentration range and absorptivity : On plotting the absorbance values of the extracts against concentration of cobalt, a straight line was obtained for 1.1-6.8 ppm of cobalt in chloroform. The optimum range⁷ for the determination was 0.9-5.3 ppm and the Sandell sensitivity⁷ $4.4 \times 10^{-8} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The molar absorptivity was $1.338 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Effect of diverse ions : The tolerance limits for different foreign ions in the determination of cobalt were studied. The results indicate that most of the ions are tolerated upto 2 to 5 mg. However, fluoride had to be used to mask Be^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and

Al^{3+} while Mg-EDTA masked As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Th^{IV} , Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . For Cr^{3+} , in addition to Mg-EDTA, hot condition was necessary. The tolerance limit of Zn^{2+} in the presence of ammonium chloride and UO_2^{2+} in the presence of tartarate was studied. The tolerance limits of Sn^{2+} in presence of sulphosalicylic acid, Hg^{2+} in presence of iodide were studied; in both the cases higher pH within the limit is recommended. For Cu^{2+} , potassium cyanide was used to mask it. The determination of nickel and cobalt was possible in the same solution. The nickel complex was first extracted into chloroform from solutions adjusted to pH below 1 and measured at 450 nm. Subsequently, cobalt was extracted from the aqueous layer by the addition of 2 ml more of reagent solution and adjusting the pH to 6.8 with γ -picoline.

Effect of masking agent : The determination of cobalt was feasible in the presence of 200 mg of each of ammonium fluoride, tartarate, acetate, citrate, sulphosalicylate, ascorbate or iodide and 2 ml of 0.01 M Mg-EDTA. However, thioglycollic acid and EDTA were found to interfere.

Precision and accuracy : The relative standard deviation for 10 determinations of cobalt was $\pm 1.6\%$. The confidence range⁸ (95%) was calculated to be $3.47 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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